

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ALISHER NAVOIY

VOLUME 5
ISSUE 1 2025

ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI

5-JILD, 1-SON

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ АЛИШЕР НАВОИЙ
ТОМ-5, НОМЕР-1

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ALISHER NAVOIY
VOLUME-5, ISSUE-1

TOSHKENT - 2025

ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ АЛИШЕР НАВОИЙ | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ALISHER NAVOIY

№1 (2025) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-1419-2025-1>

BOSH MUHARRIR: | ГЛАВНЫЙ РЕДАКТОР: | CHIEF EDITOR:

MIRZAYEV IBODULLA
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
МИРЗАЕВ ИБОДУЛЛА
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
MIRZAYEV IBODULLA
DSc, professor (Uzbekistan)

**BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI: | ЗАМЕСТИТЕЛЬ
ГЛАВНОГО РЕДАКТОРА: | DEPUTY CHIEF EDITOR:**

JABBOROV NURBOY
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
ЖАББОРОВ НУРБОЙ
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
JABBOROV NURBOY
DSc, professor (Uzbekistan)

TAHRIRIY HAY'ATI:

Muhiddinov Muslihiddin
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Sirojiddinov Shuhrat
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Rasulov Ravshanxo'ja
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Dilorom Salohiy
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Sodiqov Qosimjon
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Mark Tutan
f.f.d., professor (Fransiya)
Binnatova Almaz Ulvi
f.f.d., professor (Ozarbayjon)
To'xliyev Boqijon
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Shodmonov Nafas
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Ramiz Asker
f.f.d., professor (Ozarbayjon)
Yo'ldoshev Qozoqboy
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Jo'raqulov Uzoq
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Funda Toprak
f.f.d., professor (Turkiya)
Nabiulina Guzal
f.f.d., professor (Tatariston)
Yusupova Dilnavoz
f.f.d., dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Rahim Ibrohim
f.f.d., professor (Afg'oniston)
Suvonova Jumagul
f.f.n., dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Asadov Maqsud
f.f.d., dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Sultanov Tulkin
PhD, dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Mirzayev Rahmatilla
y.f.n., dotsent, huquqshunos (O'zbekiston)
Muhitdinova Badia
f.f.n., dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Ruzmanova Roxila
dots., mas'ul kotib (O'zbekiston)
Narziyeva Ma'mura
kotib, o'qituvchi (O'zbekiston)

ILMIY MASLAHAT KENGASHI

Toshqulov Abduqodir
i.f.d., (O'zbekiston)
Xalmuradov Rustam
t.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Eshqobil Shukur
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat
ko'rsatgan madaniyat xodimi, shoir (O'zbekiston)
To'xtasinov Ilhom
p.f.d. (O'zbekiston)
Rixsiyeva Gulchehra
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Benedek Peri
f.f.d., professor (Vengriya)
Ko'chiyev Ismat
publisist, O'zbekiston va Belorussiya
yozuvchilar uyushmasi a'zosi (O'zbekiston)
Olimov Karomatillo
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Dadaboyev Hamidulla
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Aitpayeva Gulnora
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Rahmonov Nasimxon
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Shomusarov Shorustam
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Dyu Rye Andre
f.f.d., professor (Fransiya)
Pervin Chapan
f.f.d., professor (Turkiya)
Hamroyev Juma
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Ibrohimov Elchin
f.f.n., professor (Ozarbayjon)
Jo'rayev Shokirjon
F-m.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Hasanov Shavkat
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Nurullo Oltoy
f.f.n., (Afg'oniston)
Xalliyeva Gulnoz
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Alim Labib
f.f.d., professor (Afg'oniston)
Nodira Afoqova
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)
Aftondil Erkinov
f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Мухиддинов Муслихиддин
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Сирожиддинов Шухрат
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Расулов Равшанхужа
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Дилором Салохий
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Содиков Косимжон
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Марк Тутан
д.ф.н., профессор (Франция)
Биннатова Алмаз Улви
д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)
Тухлиев Бокижон
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Шодмонов Нафас
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Рамиз Аскер
д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)
Юлдашев Казакбай
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Журакулов Узок
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Фунда Топрак
д.ф.н., профессор (Турция)
Набиуллина Гузаль
д.ф.н., профессор (Татаристан)
Юсупова Дилнавоз
д.ф.н., доцент (Узбекистан)
Рахим Иброхим
д.ф.н., профессор (Афганистан)
Сувонова Жумагул
к.ф.н., доцент (Узбекистан)
Асадов Максуд
д.ф.н., доцент (Узбекистан)
Султанов Тулкин
PhD, доцент (Узбекистан)
Мирзаев Рахматилла
к.ю.н., доцент (Узбекистан)
Мухитдинова Бадиа
к.ф.н., доцент (Узбекистан)
Рузманова Рохила
доц., отв. секретарь (Узбекистан)
Нарзиева Мамура
секретарь, преподаватель (Узбекистан)

НАУЧНО-КОНСУЛЬТАТИВНЫЙ СОВЕТ:

Тошкуллов Абдукодир
к.э.д., (Узбекистан)
Халмуратов Рустам
д.т.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Эшқобил Шукур
Заслуженный работник культуры
Республики Узбекистан, поэт (Узбекистан)
Тухтасинов Илхам
д.п.н. (Узбекистан)
Рихсиева Гулчехра
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Бенедек Пери
д.ф.н., профессор (Венгрия)
Кочиев Исмаи
Публицист, член Союза писателей
Узбекистана и Беларуси (Узбекистан)
Олимов Кароматилло
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Дадабаев Хамидулла
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Айтпаева Гулнора
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Рахмонов Насимхон
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Шомусаров Шорустам
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Дю Рье Андре
д.ф.н., профессор (Франция)
Первин Чапан
д.ф.н., профессор (Турция)
Хамроев Джума
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Иброхимов Элчин
к.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)
Джураев Шокирджон
д.ф.-м. н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Хасанов Шавкат
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Нурулло Олтой
к.ф.н., (Афганистан)
Халлиева Гулноз
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Алим Лабиб
д.ф.н., профессор (Афганистан)
Нодира Афокова
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)
Афтондил Эркинов
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD:

- Mukhiddinov Muslikhiddin**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Sirojiddinov Shukhrat**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Rasulov Ravshankhuja**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Dilorom Salokhiy**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Sodikov Kosimjon**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Mark Tutan**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (France)
- Binnatova Almaz Ulvi**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)
- Tukhliev Bokijon**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Shodmonov Nafas**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Ramiz Asker**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)
- Yuldoshev Kozokboy**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Jurakulov Uzok**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Funda Toprak**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)
- Nabiulina Guzal**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)
- Yusupova Dilnavoz**
Doc. of philol. scien., assoc. prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Rakhim Ibrokhim**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Afghanistan)
- Suvonova Jumagul**
Cand. of philol. scien., assoc. prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Asadov Makhsud**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Sultanov Tulkin**
PhD, assoc. prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Mirzayev Rahmatilla**
Cand. of legal scien., assoc. prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Mukhitdinova Badia**
Cand. of philol. scien., assoc. prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Ruzmanova Rokhila**
Assoc. prof., Exec. Sec. (Uzbekistan)
- Narziyeva Ma'mura**
Secretary, teacher (Uzbekistan)

SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY BOARD:

- Toshkulov Abdukodir**
Doc. of econ. scien., (Uzbekistan)
- Khalmuradov Rustam**
Doc. of technic. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Eshqobil Shukur**
Honored Worker of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, poet (Uzbekistan)
- Tukhtasinov Ilkhom**
Doc. of pedag. scien. (Uzbekistan)
- Rikhsieva Gulchekhra**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Benedek Peri**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Hungary)
- Kochiyev Ismat**
Publicist, member of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan and Belarus (Uzbekistan)
- Olimov Karomatullo**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Dadaboev Khamidulla**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Aitpaeva Gulnora**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Rakhmonov Nasimxon**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Shomusarov Shorustam**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Dyu Rye Andre**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (France)
- Pervin Chapan**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)
- Khamroev Juma**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Ibrokhimov Elchin**
Cand. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)
- Juraev Shokirjon**
Doc. of phys.-math. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Khasanov Shavkat**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Nurullo Oltoy**
Cand. of philol. scien., (Afghanistan)
- Khallieva Gulnoz**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Alim Labib**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Afghanistan)
- Nodira Afokova**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)
- Aftondil Erkinov**
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Page Maker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

ALISHER NAVOIYNING 583 YILLIK YUBILEYIGA BAG'ISHLANADI

Buyuk shoir va mutafakkir, atoqli davlat va jamoat arbobi Alisher Navoiyning bebaho ijodiy-ilmiy merosi nafaqat xalqimiz, balki jahon adabiyoti tarixida, milliy madaniyatimiz va adabiy-estetik tafakkurimiz rivojida alohida o'rin tutadi. Ulug' shoir o'zining she'riy va nasriy asarlarida yuksak umuminsoniy g'oyalarni, ona tilimizning beqiyos so'z boyligi va cheksiz ifoda imkoniyatlarini butun jozibasi va latofati bilan namoyon etib, yer yuzidagi millionlab kitobxonlar qalbidan munosib va mustahkam o'rin egalladi.

**O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev**

ПОСВЯЩАЕТСЯ 583 ЛЕТНОМУ ЮБИЛЕЮ АЛИШЕРА НАВОИ

Бесценное творческое и научное наследие великого поэта и мыслителя, известного государственного и общественного деятеля Алишера Навои играет важную роль в истории не только отечественной, но и мировой литературы, развитии национальной культуры и литературно-эстетического мышления. В своих лирических и прозаических произведениях великий поэт, воспевая высокие общечеловеческие идеи, демонстрировал богатый лексический запас и выразительные средства родного языка, благодаря чему занял достойное место в сердцах миллионов читателей по всему миру.

**Президент Республики Узбекистан
Шавкат Миромонович Мирзиёев**

DEDICATED TO THE 583rd ANNIVERSARY OF THE BIRTH OF ALISHER NAVOI

The invaluable creative and scientific heritage of the great poet and thinker, famous statesman and public figure Alisher Navoi has a special place not only in the history of our people, but also in the history of world literature, the development of our national culture and literary and aesthetic thinking. The great poet, in his poetic and prose works, with his whole charm and grace, has taken a worthy place in the hearts of millions of readers around the world, expressing the high universal ideas, the incomparable richness of words and the infinite possibilities of expression of our native language.

**President of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev**

AZIZ MUSHTARIY!

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyevning "Buyuk shoir va mutafakkir Alisher Navoiy tavalludining 580 yilligini keng nishonlash ro'g'risida"gi PQ-4865-son Qarorida "Alisher Navoiy asarlarida teran ifoda topgan milliy va umuminsoniy g'oyalarning jahon tamaddunida tutgan o'rmini hamda o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodning intellektual salohiyatini oshirish, ular qalbida yuksak axloqiy fazilatlarini tarbiyalashdagi beqiyos ahamiyatini nazarda tutib, shuningdek, ulug' shoir va mutafakkirning adabiy-ilmiy merosini mamlakatimizda va xalqaro miqyosda yanada chuqur tadqiq qilish va keng targ'ib etish..." lozimligi alohida ta'kidlangan.

Bu filologiya ilmi va navoiyshunoslik, xususan, adabiy ta'sir, qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, matnshunoslik va tarjima masalalari bilan shug'ullanayotgan tadqiqotchilar zimmasiga jahonning ilg'or texnologiyalari, nazariy g'oyalariga hamohang ilmiy tadqiqotlar yaratish vazifasini yuklaydi. Olimlarimizning ilmiy salohiyati, innovatsion g'oyalarini jahonda targ'ib qilish va qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida xalqaro nufuzga ega ushbu jurnal ta'sis etildi.

"Alisher Navoiy" deb nomlangan ushbu jurnalda navoiyshunoslik, Navoiy adabiy merosining umumjahon tamaddunida tutgan o'rni va adabiy ta'sir masalalari bilan shug'ullanayotgan tadqiqotchilarni o'z maqolalari bilan ishtirok etishga taklif qilamiz.

TAHRIRIYAT

УВАЖАЕМЫЙ ЧИТАТЕЛЬ!

В Постановлении №ПП-4865 Президента Республики Узбекистан Шавката Миромоновича Мирзиёева "О широком праздновании 580-летия со дня рождения великого поэта и мыслителя Алишера Навои" особо отмечается "огромное значение произведений Алишера Навои, в которых нашли глубокое отражение национальные и общечеловеческие ценности, в развитии мировой культуры, их роль в повышении интеллектуального потенциала и духовно-нравственном воспитании молодого поколения, а также в целях обеспечения дальнейшего изучения и популяризации литературно-научного наследия великого поэта и мыслителя...".

Это ставит задачи перед филологами, навоиоведами, исследователями литературного влияния, сравнительного литературоведения, текстологии и вопросов перевода создания научных исследований, соответствующих передовым мировым технологиям и теоретическим идеям. В целях пропаганды и продвижения научного потенциала и инновационных идей наших ученых учреждён данный международный журнал.

Приглашаем публиковать свои статьи в нашем журнале "Алишер Навои" отечественных и зарубежных исследователей, занимающихся изучением жизни и творчества литературы Навои, его роли в мировой литературе, проблемами литературного влияния и сравнительной поэтикой.

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИИ

DEAR READER!

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev "On the celebration of the 580th anniversary of the great poet and thinker Alisher Navoi" No PP-4865 given the invaluable role of cultivating high moral qualities in their hearts, as well as the need to further study and widely promote the literary and scientific heritage of the great poet and thinker in our country and internationally..."

This puts the task of researchers in the field of philology and Navoi studies, in particular, literary influence, comparative literature, textual studies and translation, in creating scientific research in harmony with the world's advanced technologies and theoretical ideas. This internationally renowned journal was established to promote and support the scientific potential and innovative ideas of our scientists around the world.

In this magazine, called "Alisher Navoi", we invite researchers who are interested in Navoi studies, the role of Navoi's literary heritage in world civilization and literary influence to participate with their articles.

EDITORIAL

NAVOIY NASRI VA NAZMI NAFOSATI

- 1. Sharustam SHAMUSAROV, Muslimabonu TURSUNALIYEVA**
NAVOIY VA OGAHIIY G‘AZALLARIDA HAMD TURLARI BERILISHINING QIYOSI.....10
- 2. Maftuna TURDIYEVA**
ALISHER NAVOIYNING “LAYLI VA MAJNUN” DOSTONIDA MOTIVLARNING O‘RNI...15
- 3. Zarina RAHMONOVA**
NAVOIY G‘AZALLARIDA DIALOG HODISASI.....21

ILM, OLAM VA OLIM

- 4. Maqsud ASADOV**
ADABIY TURIZM – ABADIY TURIZM ASOSI26
- 5. Iroda PARDAYEVA**
ALISHER NAVOIY IJODIDA AMIR TEMUR VA TEMURIYLAR TASVIRI.....31
- 6. Sagina HAQBERDIYEVA**
ABADIY MEROS VA ZAMONAVIY DIZAYN UCHRASHUVI: “SAB’AI SAYYOR”
TASVIRLARI ORQALI INTERYER SAN’ATI.....37
- 7. Nadim Muhammad HUMAYUN**
ALISHER NAVOIYNING “HAYRATUL-ABROR” DOSTONIDAGI “HAMMOM TASVIRI”
MINIATYURASINING TAHLILI43

NAVOIY VA ADABIY TA’SIR MASALALARI

- 8. Maftuna OCHILOVA**
NAVOIY VA YUNUS EMRE, AHMAD YASSAVIY, NESIMIY IJODLARI: G‘OYAVIY-
BADIY YAQINLIK.49
- 9. Faridaxon KARIMOVA**
XORAZM ADABIY MUHITIDA DEBOCHANAVISLIK: AN’ANA VA O‘ZIGA
XOSLIK.....56

TAQRIZ, TAHLIL VA TARJIMA

- 10. Dilorom SALOHIY**
ALISHER NAVOIY ENSIKLOPEDIYASI.....63
- 11. Roxila RUZMANOVA**
TILSHUNOS OLIM, TARJIMON MIRZAYEV IBODULLA KAMOLOVICHNING “TAHLILIIY
O‘QISH” NOMLI DARSLIGI.....68
- 12. Ibodullo MIRZAYEV**
ALISHER NAVOIY VA KOMRON MIRZO G‘AZALLARI TARJIMASI.....71

ASLIYAT UMMONI

- 13. Ibodullo MIRZAYEV**
MIRZO MUHAMMAD MEHDIXONNING “SANGLOX” ASARI (tadqiq, tafsir, tarjima va
transkripsiya).....75

NAVOIY VA TILSHUNOSLIK MASALALARI

14. Maftuna UBAYDULLAYEVA

ALISHER NAVOIY ASARLARIDA NUTQ MADANIYATIGA OID TERMINLARNING
TAHLILI.....84

MA'RIFAT YOG'DUSI

15. Alisher RAZZOQOV

NAVOIY IJODIY TAFAKKURIDA VAHDAT UL-VUJUD FALSAFASINING O'RNI HAQIDA
AYRIM MULOHAZALAR.....90

RETRO

16. G'aybulloh AS-SALOM. *Nashrga tayyorlovchi: PhD A.MAVLONOV*

ZOTI BOBARAKOT.....98

17. S.E. Malov

THE WORLD OF ALISHER NAVOI IN THE HISTORY OF TURKIC LITERATURES AND THE
LANGUAGES OF MIDDLE AND CENTRAL ASIA.....105

ISSN: 2181-1419

www.tadqiqot.uz

S.E. Malov

THE WORLD OF ALISHER NAVOI IN THE HISTORY OF TURKIC LITERATURES AND THE LANGUAGES OF MIDDLE AND CENTRAL ASIA¹

For citation: S.E.Malov. THE WORLD OF ALISHER NAVOI IN THE HISTORY OF TURKIC LITERATURES AND THE LANGUAGES OF MIDDLE AND CENTRAL ASIA. *Alisher Navoi*. 2025, vol. 5, issue 1, pp.105-111

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16933738>

ANNOTATION

In this article, academician S.E.Malov emphasizes that Alisher Navai (1441-1501), like M.V.Lomonosov, who advocated for a single Russian literary language not only with his theoretical works (primarily his Grammar), but also with his poetic compositions, had to pave the way in literature in the 15th century for the Central Asian Turkic, or Chigatai language, which has survived to this day and is now called Uzbek. As a result of the conducted research, the author comes to the conclusion that the merit of Alisher Navai is not limited to the fact that he finally legitimized the use of the Central Asian Turkic language in literature instead of Persian, that the resonance from Navai was even greater: thanks to his works, the process of the predominance of the language - "y" over the "d"-language was significantly accelerated and the Turkic "y"-language was greatly strengthened in literature throughout Chinese Turkistan, as well as in other Turkestans; Navai is not only the founder of the Uzbek literary language ("y" language), along with this, he was also among the causes, or factors, that transformed the Turkic "d"-language in Central Asia.

Key words. History of Turkic literatures, history of the languages of Central and Middle Asia, Russian literary language, Uzbek language, progenitor, poet, prose writer, "d" language, "y" language, Uyghur writing.

S.E.Malov

ALISHER NAVOIY DUNYOSI TURKIY ADABIYOTLAR VA O'RTA HAMDA MARKAZIY OSIYO TILLARI TARIXIDA

ANNOTATSIYA

Akademik S.Ye.Malovning ushbu maqolasida Alisher Navoi o'zining ilmiy ishlari (eng avvalo, grammatikasi) bilan rus tilining mustaqilligini ta'minlagan M.V.Lomonosov kabi ijodi bilan o'zbek tilining mustaqilligini, "y"lovchi til bilan "d"lovchi tilni yakqalam qilgani, O'rta Osiyoda "i"lovchi (o'zbek) tilining barqarorligini ta'minlagani ilmiy va faktik materiallar bilan asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Turkiy adabiyotlar tarixi, O'rta va Markaziy Osiyo tillari, rus adabiy tili, o'zbek tili, asoschi, shoir, nosir, "d" til, "y" til, uyg'ur yozuvi.

МИР АЛИШЕР НАВОИ В ИСТОРИИ ТЮРКСКИХ ЛИТЕРАТУР И ЯЗЫКОВ СРЕДНЕЙ И ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье академика С.Е.Малова подчеркивается, что Алишеру Наваи (1441-1501) подобно М.В.Ломоносову, ратовавшему за единый русский литературный язык не только своими теоретическими трудами (прежде всего своей Грамматикой), но и своими поэтическими сочинениями, пришлось в XV в. творить дорогу в литературе среднеазиатскому тюркскому, или чигатайскому языку, дожившему до наших дней и теперь называемому узбекским.

В результате проведенного исследования автор приходит к выводу о том, что заслуга Алишера Наваи не ограничивается тем, что им окончательно узаконено употребление в литературе среднеазиатского тюркского языка вместо персидского, что резонанс от Наваи был еще больше: благодаря его трудам, значительно ускорился процесс перевеса языка – “й” над “д” языком и весьма упрочился в литературе как во всем Китайском Туркестане, так и в других Туркестанах тюркский “й”-язык; Наваи является не только основоположником узбекского литературного языка (“й” языка), вместе с этим, был и в числе причин, или факторов, преобразовавших тюркский “д”-язык в Центральной Азии.

Ключевые слова: История тюркских литератур, история языков Средней и Центральной Азии, русский литературный язык, узбекский язык, родначальник, поэт, прозаик, “д” язык, “й” язык, уйгурская письменность.

Two centuries ago, our academician M. V. Lomonosov (1711-1765) spoke out against the then court language of the Russians, full of barbarisms, and against the bookish language, full of Church Slavonicisms. He fought for a single Russian literary language not only with his theoretical works (mainly his Grammar), but also with his poetic works. He wrote: “The most subtle philosophical imaginations and reasoning, the many different natural properties and changes that occur in this visible structure of the world and in human interactions, have decent and truly expressive speeches in our language.” He is glad that “our Russian language is not only not inferior to Greek, Latin and German in vigor and heroic ringing, but can also have a similar... natural and inherent versification.” Lomonosov finds in the Russian language “the magnificence of Spanish, the liveliness of French, the strength of German, the tenderness of Italian, and, in addition, the richness and brevity of Greek and Latin, powerful in their images.” Like Lomonosov, in the 15th century Alisher Navoi (1441-1501) had to pave the way in literature for the Central Asian Turkic, or Chagatai, language, which has survived to this day and is now called Uzbek. This modern literary and colloquial Uzbek language has, of course, gone through a long history. By our time, two groups have formed in it. In one of them, due to the proximity of the Iranian peoples surrounding the Uzbeks, some Turkic features and characteristics were partially lost. For example, the group that was called (from the 15th-16th centuries) before the October Revolution Sarts, had and has only 5-6 vowels; the other group, the Uzbeks, have 8-9; the law of Turkic synharmonism of sounds was not strictly observed in the Sart language. But both of these groups were perfectly explainable to each other, since they were, strictly speaking, historically one people, and now it would never occur to anyone to consider the Uzbeks and (former) Sarts as different peoples. Now these are not groups hostile to each other on various political and economic issues, but one people, connected, in addition to language, by one ideology, etc. If, for example, among us, Russians, someone speaks with “okanye”, then this in no way gives representatives of the aka-sounding Russian dialect the right to consider such a person a non-Russian person speaking a language other than Russian, and vice versa. Now let us move from modern times to the 15th century - the time of Alisher Navoi

Under Navoi, these two groups also existed, only they were not called Uzbeks and Sarts, but Uzbeks and Turks, and Sarts in the 15th century were still the name for Iranians by language.

Navoi was a Turk, he contrasted Turks and Uzbeks in his works, but this contrast was not for the reasons that would prevent us from considering Uzbeks and Turks as one people in the 15th century. Turks and Uzbeks, as then, in the 15th century, so Sarts and Uzbeks in the 20th century were and are one people.

It has always been clear to Turkologists that the former Sarts (after the 15th-16th centuries) and Uzbeks are two groups of the same language, which after the October Revolution is called Uzbek. Mir Alisher Navoi opposed himself to the Uzbeks, he was a Turk - Barlas - Chagatai, according to the terminology of the 15th century. We have no special reasons to change this historical terminology if we do not want to blur and obscure its specificity filled with its own special content and if we do not have sufficient and valid reasons for this. Of course, this can be done and this is done, but in this case there are no reasons for this, except for imaginary ones. This somehow preserves, even in these names, a special historical character, historical flavor of that era. And vice versa - changes in some geographic and ethnic names have great significance and revolutionary meaning for us in order to forget and erase from the area of our consciousness the dark pre-revolutionary past of these places or tribes... It is clear to every Turkologist that Navoi spoke and wrote in one of the large other groups of the Turkic (Uzbek) language, which have survived to this day. For every Turkologist, it is indisputable by virtue of this that Navoi is truly the founder or initiator of the Uzbek, in today's terminology, literary language and literature, which have been entering a new stage since the October Revolution.

Navoi is an Uzbek poet and prose writer, in our modern understanding, and not in the historical one.

If in the east of Central Asia (in Xinjiang, Gansu, not to mention Mongolia of the ancient period) the Turkic language became literary a long time ago, it already had an extensive (mainly translated) literature of Buddhist sacred books, and Manichaean and Christian literature was less extensive; Even in the 10th-14th centuries, the Turkic language, and not Arabic, was used in business legal documents on the purchase and sale of slaves, arable land, vineyards, loans, leases, etc., etc., and in tombstones, - then far to the west of Central Asia (namely in Asia Minor, in Central Asia) the Turkic language only with difficulty made its way to the right of citizenship and general recognition in literature. Here, with the spread of Islam, both in fine literature and in business acts, and even in the living speech of the upper, court class, there was the language of religion, the language of culture and statehood - the Persian language, and then the Arabic language. Mir Alisher Navoi had to assert the right to literary existence of the Central Asian Turkic language, like Lomonosov, both by scientific and theoretical treatises and by highly artistic poetic and prose works. And Navoi, in defense of his native Turkic language, wrote a theoretical treatise, "The Litigation of Two Languages," and actually proved the possibility of literature by writing many poetic literary works in prose and verse, of extremely high poetic merit. In his work, "The Litigation of Two Languages," Navoi compares the Persian and Turkic languages from the point of view of vocabulary and grammar. The Arabic language, as the language of God and the Prophet Muhammad, is, of course, beyond discussion, criticism, and comparison. The Turkic language, according to Navoi, is in no way inferior to the Persian language, and in many respects even surpasses it. Navoi proves this throughout the entire 60-80 pages.

If the Turkic language had such a hard time in Central Asia in the Muslim educated world, where Arabic and Persian were dominant, then the position of the Turkic language in Asia Minor was only slightly easier. Here, only no more than two hundred years before Navoi, the Turkish language began to win the right of citizenship. Here, the first Turkish, properly Seljuk, authors - Jelyaluddin Rumi (d. 1273) and his son Sultan Veled (d. 1312), writing in Turkish, even apologize for trying to clothe high, divine theological truths in the language of the Turks. To say without any reservations that before Navoi the Turkic language was not used in literature in Central Asia would be completely incorrect: this would not correspond to real historical data. Navoi himself in his historical and literary work "Majalis-un-nafais" ("Collection of Rare People") points to a number of great contemporary poets and his predecessors, whom he values very highly for their literary talent and who wrote in the Turkic language (for example, Lutfi, Atai). Moreover, long before Navoi, in the 12th century, in the present-day town of Turkestan, formerly called "Yasi", lived and wrote his "Divan-i hikmet" ("Book

of Wisdom") Khoja Ahmed Yaseviysky, i.e. Yassky, Turkestansky, i.e. from the city of Turkestan, in a Turkic language that every modern Uzbek, albeit of the old generation, considers completely his own, native, close and Uzbek. The works of Akhmed Yaevi are now readable and understandable for the older generation, and this, of course, is due to the conditions of the time. In terms of content, it is clear that this work is not suitable for wide reading by our Uzbek youth, it is a mystical-religious (Sufi) work, and the vocabulary, perhaps, will also greatly hinder understanding. Nowadays, knowledge of Arabic and Persian is less widespread among modern educated Uzbeks than before. The same, of course, must be said about Navoi. After all, he wrote 500 years ago, was a very educated man of Muslim culture, in the rank of vizier (minister - lord keeper of the seal), knew, as he himself reports, the Persian language perfectly. It is not surprising that now, just as we Russians accompany our linguistic monument, The Tale of Igor's Campaign (12th century), with a list of rare, obscure and obsolete words, so the Uzbeks, if anyone has seen Navoi's publications, have to accompany them with a list, and not even a list, but a whole dictionary of these now obscure and rarely used in the Uzbek language, mainly Arabic and Persian words, with their translation into the Uzbek language modern to us. As for Akhmed Yasevi, in the 12th century, like other rare old authors, he was, of course, an exception. These wonderful springs of folk Turkic speech could not then, in the old days, break through the thickness of the accepted literary traditions with the Arabic and Persian languages. And only with the work of Navoi was the use of the Turkic language clearly strengthened in the literature of Central Asia. And this is no small merit of Navoi, his poetic and prose works. But I would like to point out another significance of Navoi in the history of Turkic literatures and languages. For this, let us turn a little further east from Central Asia, let us turn our gaze to the expanses of Central Asia in a broader sense, or to Central Asia.

During Navoi's lifetime, in the 15th century, here in Central Asia, two major religions clashed: Islam from the West and Buddhism from the East and South, and two cultures clashed: Islamic (Arab-Persian) and Buddhist (Tibetan-Indian-Chinese), and two scripts and alphabets clashed: Arabic, which ran from West to East, and the Mughur alphabet, which ran from East to West. But that's not all. In Central Asia in the 15th century, two linguistic elements clashed in their final battle for existence. The Turkic language - "y" from the West and the Turkic language - "d" from the East. I will explain this with examples. If in the West they said "ayak" (leg), then in the East, where there was a "d" language, they pronounced this word "adak". Or: in the West - "koy" (to put), "toy" (to be saturated), and in the East - "kod" and "tod", etc. Of course, here I am indicating a very bright (and universally accepted) classification feature (also, see below, numerals), which entails other features inherent in each of these two languages separately. Chinese Turkestan was the arena of these opposing warring currents, or trends: it was here in the 15th century, during the life and work of Navoi, that Islam finally triumphed over Buddhism, which had given way to it here. Since the 15th century, the Turks of Chinese Turkestan have finally accepted Islam and Islamic Persian-Arabic culture. This whole process of Islamization had been going on since the 8th century, but since the 15th century Chinese Turkestan has become, strictly speaking, finally what it is now, i.e. a Muslim country with all the qualities inherent in this. Christianity and Manichaeism came to naught simultaneously with Buddhism. But these religions had fewer Uighur confessors in Central Asia and, one must think, died out, of course, even before the 15th century. I will add that the traveler Marco Polo (13th century) still found Christians in the cities of Chinese Turkestan; he visited the Christian temples of the Uyghurs and sang hymns to the Virgin Mary "Ave, Maria!" in them.

In Central Asia, in contrast to the western part of Asia, the Turkic language had long ago acquired the rights of citizenship. Almost all Buddhist books, which constitute the main official Buddhist canon of sacred books, were translated into this language.

Translations into the Turkic Uyghur language were made from different languages, most of all from the Chinese language. Translations were also made from Tibetan, Indian (Sanskrit), from Tocharian.

We do not know now whether Navoi knew this Buddhist, Christian and Manichaean literature. After all, there could not have been any particular difficulty in reading this literature in the "d" language for a representative of the Turkic "y" language, given such an educated person as Alisher

Navoi was. He mentions Uyghur literature in passing (2-3 times). But what he meant by this is unknown. It is possible that he meant Muslim literature in the Uyghur "d" language of Chinese Turkestan. Let us not forget that Navoi was too much of a Westerner and, moreover, a Muslim for whom Buddhism and Christianity were idolatry. During Navoi's time, Muslim literature in the "d" Uyghur language was also widespread (and specifically in Central Asia, not in Central Asia). It was in Herat, Navoi's place of residence, that this didactic Muslim literature was copied and read mainly. Here we can mention "The Book of Happiness" (11th century), "The Gift of Truths" (12th century), several 14th century Korans translated into the Turkic literary (Uyghur) language, and other things. For some reason, for a very long time in the lands of Central Asia in all three Turkestans - Western, Eastern and Afghan, already under the dominance of strongly strengthened and spread Islam together with its Arabic script, one can see works written not only in Arabic script, but also in the Uyghur alphabet. We have several more bi-alphabet (Arabic-Uyghur) manuscripts of Chagatai poets. It can also be noted that in 1469, the father of Sultan Babur in Andijan, Omar-sheikh, gives a preferential document to the Marginan (Margilan) nobleman Mir Seyid Ahmed, written in Uyghur letters; the language of this document, if not Uyghur, then in any case bears some imprint of the Uyghur language. Recently, another charter from 1468 of Sultan Abu Said, who was the father of Omar-sheikh, was found in Turkey. This charter is written in two alphabets - Uyghur and Arabic (published by Nimet Kurat in Istanbul in 1940). But even these things in Central Asia were already to some extent an anachronism during the time of Navoi. I mean the Uyghur script and the "d" language. They were copied and owned only by lovers of antiquity, aesthetes. Such societies, or circles, of aestheto-archaeologists, lovers of antiquity were, perhaps, as I said, in Herat in the 15th century during the time of Navoi, since from this city we have several manuscripts written in two alphabets: Uyghur and Arabic, for example, "The Gift of Truths", a work by the poet Lutfi5, "The Book of Happiness" (Kutadgu Bilig) of the 11th century, etc. e letters go from top to bottom and lines from left to right. This Uyghur alphabet was borrowed by the Mongols, since the Uyghurs were once the teachers of the Mongols in ancient times. But this is not enough. If earlier, in ancient times, among the Turks, literary movements, vocabulary and in general the influence of the Turkic language were directed from the east to the west, then later, in the Middle Ages, in terms of the Turkic language, the movement went from the west to the east. This, for example, is very clearly visible if we compare at least the "Book of Happiness" of the 11th century with legal documents of the 11th-14th centuries. The Book of Happiness (from Kashgar) already contains many Arabic and Persian words. This book is entirely of Muslim culture. We can add here that at the same time, in the 12th century, a native of Kashgar, Mahmud, wrote his three-volume work on the Turkic languages entirely in Arabic; further to the east, at the same time or even a hundred years later, in the legal documents of the Turks from Turfan, we will find almost no Arabic and Persian words. In all the documents known to us, there are no more than half a dozen Arabic and Persian words. Of course, Arabic and Persian words needed time to penetrate from Kashgar further to the east, to the Turfan oasis, for example. It would seem that it would be very appropriate for Arabic words to fill all these legal documents, but this did not happen. The Uighurs developed their own terminology. The movement of language in the Middle Ages from west to east is also evident from the use of the counting system in these same written monuments. The Western (new) counting system gradually moved east. In the 11th century, the old counting system no longer existed in Kashgar, but in Turfan it was still used in legal documents until the 13th-14th centuries, and even further to the east, beyond the Great Wall of China, among the contemporary Buddhist Uighurs - the Yellow Uighurs, the old, not the new, counting system has been preserved and is used even now. The difference between the old and new systems is that now numbers from tens and units are expressed in such a way that the larger number, i.e. ten is placed first, and units come in second place; for example, eleven in Tatar will be "ten one", and so it is everywhere, with the exception of the contemporary Yellow Uighurs of the Chinese province of Gansu.

From the West, as I said, Islam was moving to the East. Along with this movement came Arabic education and, of course, the Arabic alphabet to replace the Uyghur alphabet previously used by the Turks, where the letters go from top to bottom and the lines go from left to right. This Uyghur alphabet was borrowed by the Mongols, since the Uyghurs were once the teachers of the Mongols in ancient

times. But this is not enough. If earlier, in ancient times, among the Turks, literary movements, vocabulary and, in general, the influence of the Turkic language were directed from the East to the West, then later, in the Middle Ages, in terms of the Turkic language, the movement went from the West to the East. This, for example, is very clearly visible if we compare at least the "Book of Happiness" of the 11th century with legal documents of the 11th-14th centuries. The Book of Happiness (from Kashgar) already contains many Arabic and Persian words. This book is entirely of Muslim culture. We can add here that at the same time, in the 12th century, a native of Kashgar, Mahmud, wrote his three-volume work on the Turkic languages entirely in Arabic; further to the east, at the same time or even a hundred years later, in the legal documents of the Turks from Turfan, we will find almost no Arabic and Persian words. In all the documents known to us, there are no more than half a dozen Arabic and Persian words. Of course, Arabic and Persian words needed time to penetrate from Kashgar further to the east, to the Turfan oasis, for example. It would seem that it would be very appropriate for Arabic words to fill all these legal documents, but this did not happen. The Uighurs developed their own terminology. The movement of language in the Middle Ages from west to east is also evident from the use of the counting system in these same written monuments. The Western (new) counting system gradually moved east. In the 11th century, the old counting system no longer existed in Kashgaria, but in Turfan it was still used in legal documents until the 13th - 14th centuries, and even further to the east, behind the Great Wall of China, among the contemporary Buddhist Uighurs - the Yellow Uighurs, the old, not the new, counting system was preserved and is used even now. The difference between the old and new systems is that now numbers from tens and units are expressed in such a way that the larger number, i.e., the ten is placed first, and the units come in second place; for example, eleven in Tatar is "ten one", and so it is everywhere, with the exception of the modern yellow Uyghurs of the Chinese province of Gansu.

In ancient times, and among the Gansu Uighurs even now, "eleven" was and is expressed through "one twenty"; "thirty three" will be expressed through "three forty". By the 15th-16th centuries (this is, of course, very approximately) religion was changing in Central Asia, along with which the alphabet was changing and even the language was gradually changing in part: it was moving from the "d" language to the Turkic "y" language, which this language continues to be in Chinese Turkestan at the present time. I would like to think that in this general movement of culture from west to east, Navoi was not only captured and carried away by the flow, no, he himself, one must think, partly moved and directed this flow of language and literature. He was not only a fact, but also a factor in history. Navoi contributed to the rapid spread of the Turkic language and literature from the West with his brilliant poem-novels. He was an extremely beloved, widely read author, and this is evidenced by the numerous manuscripts of his works that have come down to us from different centuries. And at the present time in Chinese Turkestan, even in the remote corners of Lop-Nor, Navoi's poems are read, sung and recited. The plots of his poems are told in the form of separate tales and stories, etc. I heard all this directly myself. Travelers in Central Asia, for example the Swedish traveler Sven Hedin, tell us the same thing. In a word, Navoi's influence reached the Great Wall of China along with the "y" language. The influence of the West, and along with it the influence of Navoi, did not go further than the Chinese Wall: the yellow Uighurs of Gansu know nothing about Islam; I cannot say anything about the Salars who live along the Hoan-he River, near the mountains of Xiong-hua-ting, and who profess Islam, whether they read the works of Navoi, due to the lack of data.

It goes without saying that Alisher Navoi was copied and read and is read in Central Asia, and in Tataria, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Afghanistan, India...

Alisher Navoi's merits are not limited to the fact that he finally legitimized the use of the Central Asian Turkic language in literature instead of Persian. As we see, the resonance from Navoi was even greater: thanks to his works, the process of the predominance of the "y" language over the "d" language was significantly accelerated and the Turkic "y" language became very strong in literature throughout Chinese Turkestan, as well as in other Turkestans. Navoi is not only the founder of the Uzbek literary language (the "y" language), no, he was also one of the causes or factors that

transformed the Turkic "d" language in Central Asia. If all of the above is accepted, then the significance and influence of Alisher Navoi is much greater than it seemed to us until now.

Reference

1. Reported (abridged) at a meeting of the Department of Literature and Language of the USSR Academy of Sciences.
2. On the Sarts, see the jury. "Zhivaya Starina", 1910, issue III. Cf. Acad. V. V. Struve, Kh. I. Muratov and V. I. Kalyanov, Institute of Oriental Studies, see Bulletin of the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1937, No. 10-11, p. 266.
3. Cf. "Alisher Navoi", collection of articles, published by the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1946, pp. 96, 102 and 120.
4. Cf. Abul-Gaz i, Genealogical tree of the Turks, translation and preface by G.S. Sablukov, Kazan, 1906, (1914), p. VI.
5. See Notes of the Eastern Separate Russian Archival Society, Vol. XXIV, P., pp. 228 and 232.

ALISHER NAVOIY HAYKALI. KECİO‘REN, ANQARA, TURKIYA.
Haykal 2024-yilda Kechio‘ren tumanida O‘zbekiston va Turkiya o‘rtasidagi do‘stlik hamda ma‘naviy hamkorlik ramzi sifatida o‘rnatilgan.

ПАМЯТНИК АЛИШЕРУ НАВОИ. КЕЧИОРЕН, АНКАРА, ТУРЦИЯ.
Памятник был установлен в районе Кечиорен в 2024 году как символ дружбы и духовного сотрудничества между Узбекистаном и Турцией.

STATUE OF ALISHER NAVOI. KECİIOREN, ANKARA, TÜRKİYE.
The statue was erected in district of Kechioren in 2024 as a symbol of friendship and spiritual cooperation between Uzbekistan and Türkiye.

**“ALISHER NAVOIY”
XALQARO
JURNALNING
AXBOROT XATI**

“Alisher Navoiy” xalqaro jurnali O‘zbekiston Respublikasi OAK ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan. Shuningdek, Crossref.org tizimiga ham kiritiladi hamda har bir maqolaga DOI raqami beriladi.

**MAQOLALARGA
QO‘YILADIGAN TALABLAR:**

- Maqola 10-15 sahifa hajmida taqdim etiladi;
- maqolalar o‘zbek, turk, tojik, rus, ingliz, fransuz tillarida qabul qilinadi;
- maqolaning tarkibiy tuzilishi IMRAD formatida rasmiylashtirilishi kerak;
- maqola Times News Roman shriftida, 12 kattalikda, 1 intervalda tayyorlanadi;
- havola(snoskalar)lar katta qavsda muallif familiyasi – nashr sanasi – sahifasi [Mo‘minov 2020: 25] shaklida keltiriladi;
- maqola tomonlari chap: 2 sm, o‘ng: 2 sm, yuqori va quyi: 2 sm;
- maqolalar plagiatga qarshi tekshiriladi;
- jurnalning 1 ta sonida muallifning faqat 1 ta maqolasi chop etiladi.

MUROJAAT UCHUN MANZIL:
Tel.: +99891 527 68 22
Telegram ID: +998915276822
E-mail: alishernavoiy2020@mail.ru

**ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЕ
ПИСЬМО
МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО
ЖУРНАЛА
“АЛИШЕР НАВОИ”**

Международный журнал “Алишер Навои” включен в список ВАК Республики Узбекистан. Он также будет включен в систему Crossref.org, и каждой статье будет присвоен номер DOI.

**ТРЕБОВАНИЯ К
ОФОРМЛЕНИЮ СТАТЕЙ:**

- Объем статьи: около 10-15 страниц;
- статьи принимаются на узбекском, турецком, таджикском, русском, английском и французском языках;
- структура статьи должна быть оформлена в формате IMRAD;
- шрифт текста – Times New Roman; размер – 12 пунктов; межстрочный интервал – 1;
- сноски приводятся в квадратных скобках с указанием фамилии автора – года издания – страницы [Мўминов 2020: 25];
- параметры страницы: слева 2 см, справа 2 см, сверху и снизу по 2 см;
- статьи проверяются на плагиат;
- в одном номере журнала публикуется только 1 статья автора.

НАШИ КОНТАКТЫ:
Тел.: +99891 527 68 22
Telegram ID: +998915276822
E-mail: alishernavoiy2020@mail.ru

**“ALISHER NAVOI”
INTERNATIONAL
JOURNAL INFORMATION
LETTER**

“Alisher Navoi” International Journal is included in the list of HAC of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It will also be included in the Crossref.org system, and each article will be assigned a DOI number.

**REQUIREMENTS FOR
ARTICLES:**

- The article should be presented in 10-15 pages;
- articles are accepted in Uzbek, Turkish, Tajik, Russian, English, French;
- the structure of the article should be in the IMRAD format.
- the article should be prepared in Times New Roman font, 12 sizes, 1 space;
- references are given in parentheses in the form of the author’s name – date of publication - page [Muminov 2020: 25];
- sides of the article left: 2 cm, right: 2 cm, top and bottom: 2 cm;
- articles will be checked against plagiarism.
- only 1 article by the author is published in 1 issue of the journal.

CONTACT ADDRESS:
Phone: +99891 527 68 22
Telegram ID: +998915276822
E-mail: alishernavoiy2020@mail.ru

ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI

5-JILD, 1-SON

**МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ АЛИШЕР НАВОИЙ
ТОМ-5, НОМЕР-1**

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ALISHER NAVOIY
VOLUME-5, ISSUE-1**

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000